

What Is Socially Responsible Research, and How Do We Teach It?

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Abstract

Young researchers can drive meaningful change. With guidelines and playful e-modules, we help them embed social and environmental responsibility into every stage of research. We call on global communities to adopt and evolve these tools to make responsible science routine.

Introduction

In the face of complex societal challenges such as climate change, global health inequities, the reproducibility crisis, and widening social disparities, science must not only look inward, but also act outward. Young researchers and clinicians are aware of this responsibility and motivated to make a positive difference through their work. Yet, turning this awareness into practice can be difficult. While information on open science, sustainability, and equity is increasingly available, it can be hard to know where to start or how to integrate these concepts meaningfully.

Tools for Socially Responsible Research

In this Community Page, we address this gap by introducing three open-access, modular tools designed to make socially responsible research accessible, practical, and engaging. Developed within (bio)medical education and research, these tools are equally relevant for other scientific disciplines seeking to integrate social and environmental responsibility into their work. The set includes the *Guidelines for Socially Responsible Research* (1) and two interactive e-modules (2,3) in which the participant learns about scientific, ecological, and societal impact across the research and experimental cycles. Each can be used independently or combined as part of a broader learning sequence. Together, they provide structure, clarity, and inspiration for students, young researchers, supervisors, and educators who wish to translate the values of socially responsible research into everyday scientific practice.

Guidelines for Socially Responsible Research

The *Guidelines for Socially Responsible Research* were developed to support (future) researchers in designing, conducting, and disseminating biomedical research in a socially responsible manner. Structured around the research cycle (Figure 1A), the guidelines provide a practical checklist, simply formulated reflective questions, and links to supportive resources that help researchers consider open science principles, equality, and ecological sustainability throughout all phases of their work. It highlights how responsible research

practices can reduce the environmental footprint and minimise wasted research efforts by promoting evidence-based design, collaboration, and the co-development of research questions with stakeholders such as patients and practitioners. To this end, the guidelines refer to existing best practices and frameworks, including the SAGER guidelines for sex and gender equity (4), the Genderful Research World platform (5), the James Lind Alliance for research priority setting (6), the Bias-Free Language guidelines (7), the R-ladder for circularity, and the EQUATOR Network for transparent reporting (8).

E-Modules: Journey to Nova

To make the concepts from the guidelines more tangible, two e-modules invite learners to explore socially responsible research through play and reflection, and provide background information, useful tips, and guidance. These playfully illustrated e-modules take learners on a journey to the fictional planet *Nova*, where research is organized around just and sustainable practices. Each 60-minute module follows the experimental cycle and invites users to collect ideas and strategies to apply in their own research context.

In *Just & Sustainable Research Practices* (Figure 2A), learners explore how responsible research contributes to the health of both people and ecosystems. Themes include avoiding wasted research efforts through evidence-based approaches, bias in science, responsible data management, open science, and inclusive communication. The module also introduces participatory approaches, such as involving patients or practitioners in setting research priorities.

In *Just & Sustainable Laboratory Research* (Figure 2B), the focus shifts towards sustainability in experimental laboratory work. Learners examine environmental impacts and explore practical strategies for improvement through topics such as energy and resource use, waste reduction, animal-free research, and engagement with sustainable laboratory communities.

The guidelines are especially useful when preparing or reviewing research proposals, while the e-modules provide hands-on training, particularly for students entering research or laboratory spaces. Together, they help researchers reflect on the balance between scientific, societal, and environmental impact (Figure 1B).

A Call for Action

At the University Medical Center Utrecht (UMC Utrecht), the aforementioned tools are being embedded across educational programmes, as part of a growing movement to integrate planetary health and social responsibility into (bio)medical training. Within the UMC Utrecht, a dedicated *Planetary Health Integration Team* brings together educators and support staff from different disciplines to co-develop and implement these tools and concepts. Faculty leadership has enabled this work by allocating time and resources for the development of planetary health education: an essential step in creating sustainable change.

In the MSc Clinical Health Sciences, which trains experienced healthcare professionals to become scientific researchers in their field, students complete the e-module '*Just and Sustainable Science Practices*', and use the guidelines in setting-up and executing a clinical research project as part of their academic training. The e-module is completed in the first weeks of the course to give students a solid foundation into what it means to do socially responsible research. In the weeks following, students are asked to reflect on the questions in the guidelines that are relevant to the phase of the research cycle they are in, and to make adjustments to their research accordingly. This implementation highlights just one of the many ways these tools can be incorporated into research education, and we are now working to formally assess their impact.

In addition to local or national efforts, the UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) network recently adapted the e-module '*Just & Sustainable Laboratory Research*' into a European version (9), demonstrating how such resources can evolve through international collaboration. We invite educators, students, and green teams to join this movement by using and further developing the tools, sharing best practices, and connecting within emerging communities of practice. For institutions, meaningful change requires vision, supportive policy, and capacity to embed socially responsible research education in local learning environments, for which *Whole Institution Approach* would provide a useful supporting tool. We invite institutional leadership to take action. Initiatives like the Planetary Health Integration Team provide an effective governance model for such integration. Ultimately, while these tools offer practical guidance, the broader transformation lies in reimagining education itself, where social and environmental responsibility are not peripheral topics but integral components of what it means to do science well.

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Figure 1. Panel A shows the research cycle as is described in the E-modules and guidelines, as well as a representation of the stakeholders that are taken along during the research cycle. Panel B shows the triangle of research, balancing scientific value with the ecological footprint and societal value of the research.

Figure 2. Panel A shows the cover of the E-module ‘Just and Sustainable Science Practices’. Panel B shows the cover of the E-module ‘Just and Sustainable Laboratory Research’.